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GrInShield newsletter

5th

GrInShield has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Actions under grant agreement No. 101079151.

In the 5th newsletter of the GrInShield project, you can find the most important information about activities conducted within the project.

In the past months, GrInShield organized one onsite training, a meeting with stakeholders, worked on the development of the skills of administration staff by organizing online and onsite training and lectures, visited a highly successful startup company in the country of advanced partner, and conducted various experiments, and collected many, many outstanding results! The team was working on finishing the preparations for the Monography entitled "Electromagnetic shielding materials – Graphene-based composites and beyond" currently in the production stage.

In the following part, you can find more details.

I GrInShield Trainings

3rd Onsite training at FTPO, Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

From November 13–15, 2024, the third GrInShield Onsite Training, titled "*Polymer Processing and Studying Mechanical Characteristics*," was held at the Faculty of Polymer Technology (FTPO) in Slovenj Gradec. This hybrid event was tailored for students of chemistry, physics, materials science, and early-career researchers with an interest in polymer technology. The first day began with introductory lectures by FTPO team member Janez Slapnik, focusing on the mechanical properties of various polymers and the methodologies used for testing them. In the afternoon, participants engaged in hands-on experiments, measuring the mechanical properties of two different polymers using a universal testing machine. Day two was dedicated to both the theoretical background and practical testing of mechanical properties. Led by FTPO team member Sylvester Bolka, participants explored the significance of impact testing and other essential evaluation techniques. The third and final day focused on data analysis. The participants were guided through the interpretation of DMA (Dynamic Mechanical Analysis) results using advanced software tools. The training concluded with a microscopy session, offering a closer look at glass fibers under a light microscope and revealing captivating details about their structure and behavior.

II GrInShield administration and management developing actions – building strong administration in collaboration with advanced EU offices CNRS - UL online training/meeting with VINCA team

Under the lead of Prof. Dr. Kamel Haddadi, the training entitled „General Rules for EU Project Administration“ was delivered by Hervé Avelin from IEMN CNRS, and Adrien Cammarata from CNRS Regional Delegation on December 10th, 2024, online. Members of the VINCA office for the project implementation, Dr. Adzic, Ana Jutic, Dr. Vukoje, and others, along with GrInShield members, Dr. Jovanović and Dr. Kepić, participated in comprehensive training and an open discussion about work time tracking, eligible costs, and task allocation between administrative staff and many other topics. By sharing their vast management experience and practical knowledge, Hervé Avelin and Adrien Cammarata made a crucial contribution to the importance of collaboration in the Office for project implementation, the sector of the coordinating institution that is being developed.

Visit to FTPO

On Monday, 16th December 2024, GrInShield's activity was focused on **administration and management**. Our team members organized meetings in **FTPO** with their administrative and management staff, sharing their experience in project monitoring and implementation. Both **VINCA** and **FTPO** employees shared their experiences, best practices, and discussed approaches to improve efficiency in task implementation and understanding between administrative and scientific staff. A visit was organized by the GrInShield project in association with the WeBaSOOP project (GA 101060170), while participants were administrative and magnet staff from both organizations: Blaž Nardin, Maja Mešl, Viktorija Zanoškar, Miroslav Adžić, Ana Jutić, Milena Marjanović, Marina Ilić, Milena Jovašević, Miloš Živanovic, Dejan Kepić, and Svetlana Jovanović.

III GrInShield team at the conferences and events **Fourth Serbian-French Innovation Forum**

The GrInShield team members participated in the **Fourth Serbian-French Innovation Forum**, where researchers and innovators from both the Republic of Serbia and France came together under the slogan "*AI-deas for a better tomorrow: driving societal change!*". The event provided a great platform to connect, exchange ideas, establish collaboration with AI experts, and spark new R&D collaborations in priority areas while also encouraging participation in Horizon Europe programs. The event was organized by the **Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Serbia, the French Embassy, the French Institute, the Palace of Science, Tempus Foundation, and French Tech** and took place at the Palace of Serbia.

Tesla Innovation Days Conference

GrInShield's results were presented at **the Third Conference "Tesla Innovation Days - TID"** held between April 7 and 8th, 2025, at the Radisson Collection Hotel in Belgrade.

The conference was organized by **the Nikola Tesla Institute of Electrical Engineering, Belgrade**. GrInShield coordinator **Svetlana Jovanović** presented a lecture entitled *„Innovation in EMI shielding materials integrated in GrInShield project“*.

The conference gathered experts from various research fields to address current challenges and prospects in the energy sector, focusing on the application of nuclear energy for sustainable development, the integration of artificial intelligence in energy system management, and advanced solutions for power transmission and distribution networks. GrInShield results regarding shielding new nanomaterials attract great attention, especially from experts in non-ionizing measurements, professional safety, and protection.

IV Building a strategic network of stakeholders within the GrInShield project Stockholder meeting

In collaboration with 4 Horizon Europe projects, BIOLAWEB (101079234), EINSTEIN (101136377), STEPUPIORS (101079217), and startup Dirigent Acoustics, the GrInShield team co-organized a stakeholder meeting in the Science and Technology Park Belgrade in Belgrade, Serbia, on December 9th, 2024.

With over 80 participants from the academic, business sectors, and policymakers, 3 Horizon Europe projects gather around one idea - to create a healthier environment for future generations!

The GrInShield team organized a session raising concerns about non-ionizing irradiation, measurements, and displaying obtained results within the project, while with Dr. Malgorzata Celuch from **QWED Sp. z o.o., Poland**, presented a lecture entitled “Computational modelling and microwave characterisation tools to support the development of electromagnetic shielding materials”.

Another important concern was addressed by the **CEO of Dirigent Acoustics**, Dejan Todorovic, highlighting the effects of noise and how graphene membranes could be used in acoustics and the detection of noise.

The meeting was officially supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia, the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Serbia, the Center for the 4th Industrial Revolution in Serbia, and the Delegation of the European Union to Serbia.

Of the **95** registered participants, 60% came from **14 different academic institutions**, the rest from **10 business companies**, **9 government institutions**, and **1 non-profit** organization. The meeting highlighted the importance of trans-sectoral collaborations, interconnecting different scientific fields with policymakers towards a healthier society, supporting the goals of the World Health Organization's One Health agenda.

More at link

<https://www.euronews.rs/biznis/biznis-vesti/149200/naucni-skup-brze-reakcije-su-kljucne-z-a-poboljsanje-zdravlja-ljudi-i-zivotne-sredine-u-srbiji/vest>

Celebration of Dirigent Acoustics 18th birthday

The GrInShield team was honored to receive special recognition from the stakeholders and collaborators, the startup company Dirigent Acoustics LLC, on the 26th of February 2025, during their 18th birthday celebration!

Visit to the SmarAct company

With association with prof. dr.-ing. Olaf C. Haenssler, PhD, IU **International University of Applied Sciences**, GrInShield team members Mila Milenković, Dejan Kepić, Muhammad Yasir, and Svetlana Jovanović visited **SmarAct** on April 23rd, 2025. The host, Michael Weigel-Jech (CEO SmarAct BU Motion and BU Automation), presented an outstanding SmarAct path toward becoming one of the largest and most successful startup companies. In the inspirational and empowering discussion, the importance of nurturing a supportive working environment, human capacity, and personal motivation were highlighted as key factors for SmarAct's skyrocketing growth. Dr. -ing. Olaf C. Haenssler and Michael Weigel-Jech shared with the GrInShield team practical, legal, and financial aspects of developing high-tech businesses.

V GrInShield publications

The GrInShield team has published several papers in the past 6 months and submitted a few more!

„**Carbonized Apples and Quinces Stillage for Electromagnetic Shielding**“ is a pioneer study describing the process of converting biowaste collected after schnapps distillation into EMI shielding material! The paper was published in *Nanomaterials* (<https://www.mdpi.com/2079-4991/14/23/1882>) on 23rd November 2024, showing the astonishing efficacy to block incident electromagnetic waves of nearly 80% at 10 GHz.

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Carbonized Apples and Quinces Stillage for Electromagnetic Shielding

by Mila Milenkovic¹, Warda Saeed², Muhammad Yasir^{2*}, Dusan Milivojevic¹, Ali Azmy³, Kamal E. S. Nassar³, Zois Syrgiannis³, Ioannis Spanopoulos³, Danica Bajuk-Bogdanovic⁴, Snežana Maletić⁵, Djurdja Kerkez⁵, Tanja Barudzija¹ and Svetlana Jovanović^{1,*}

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GrInShield team published the scientific paper entitled **“Microwave Electromagnetic Shielding of Free-Standing Composites of Silver Nanowires Sandwiched Between Graphene Oxide or Reduced Graphene Oxide Layers”** (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12213-025-00184-5>) in the **Journal of Micro and Bio Robotics**. This work highlights the potential of silver nanowires and graphene-based materials to enhance electromagnetic shielding properties.

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Microwave electromagnetic shielding of free-standing composites of silver nanowires sandwiched between graphene oxide or reduced graphene oxide layers

Research | Published: 04 February 2025
Volume 21, article number 2, (2025) [Cite this article](#)

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Dejan Kečić , Ana Pantić, Warda Saeed, Muhammad Yasir & Svetlana Jovanović

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Another GrInShield team's paper entitled “**Study of Graphene Oxide and Silver Nanowires Interactions and Its Association with Electromagnetic Shielding Effectiveness**” which highlights the potential of silver nanowires and graphene-based materials in electromagnetic shielding was published in the **International Journal of Molecular Sciences**. How we interconnected theoretical analyses and experimental results, you can read on the link: <https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/25/24/13401>.

The screenshot shows the article page on the MDPI website. On the left is a sidebar with the journal logo, submission buttons, and an article menu. The main content area displays the article title, authors (Mila Milenković, Warda Saeed, Muhammad Yasir, Dusan Sredojević, Milica Budimir, Andjela Stefanović, Danica Bajuk-Bogdanović, and Svetlana Jovanović), their affiliations, and the article's DOI. It also includes submission and publication dates, a download button, and a share icon. The right sidebar contains social media and utility icons.

How could biochar, scaffolds, rare earth, and ferrite composites be used as a barrier for non-ionizing irradiation?

The GrInShield team explored these 4 different materials in a new cutting-edge paper, exploring the latest trends in developing new EMI shielding materials.

The paper entitled „**New Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Materials: Biochars, Scaffolds, Rare Earth, and Ferrite-Base Materials**” (<https://doi.org/10.3390/nano15070541>) was published in **Nanomaterials** as a part of the special issue „**Advanced Nanomaterials for Electromagnetic Shielding and Absorption Applications**”.

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New Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Materials: Biochars, Scaffolds, Rare Earth, and Ferrite-Based Materials

by Dragana Marinković^{1,*}, Slađana Dorončić¹, Dejan Kepić¹, Kamel Haddadi², Muhammad Yasir³, Blaž Nardin⁴ and Svetlana Jovanović^{1,*}¹ Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, P.O. Box 522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia² University of Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille, University Polytechnique Hauts-de-France, UMR 8520-IEMN- Institut d'Electronique de Microélectronique et de Nanotechnologie-Lille, 59650 Villeneuve-d'Ascq, France³ Department of Computer Science, Division of Microrobotics and Control Engineering, University of Oldenburg, Ammerländer Heerstraße 114-118, 26129 Oldenburg, Germany⁴ Faculty of Polymer Technology, Ozare 19, 2380 Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

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